

SUBTRACTION SCHEMES FOR THE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY EQUATION

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ISSIQLIK O'TKAZUVCHANLIK TENGLAMASI UCHUN AYIRMALI SXEMALAR

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abstract

In the same-sex environment, heat transfer nets for one dimension have been constructed and studied.

аннотация

В однополых средах теплопроводность сетки для одного размера изучается структурой.

annotatsiya

Bir jinsli muhitda, bir o'lcham uchun issiqlik o'tkazilishi to'rlar tuzilib o'rganilgan.

Keywords:

finite subtraction method, boundary nodes, inner nodes, layer.

Ключевые слова:

метод конечных вычетов, граничные узлы, внутренние узлы, слой.

Kalit so'zlar:

chekli ayirmalar usuli, chegaraviy tugunlari, ichki tugunlar, qatlam.

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The one-dimensional non-stationary thermal conductivity equation becomes

$$c_p \rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + \bar{f}, \quad (1)$$

in this $u = u(x, t)$ - temperature, c_p - unit mass heat capacity, ρ – density, k – coefficient of thermal conductivity, $\bar{f}$ - density of heat sources, that is, the amount of heat released from unit length at Unit time. If, then $c_p = c_p(x, t, u)$, $k = k(x, t, u)$ – the equation is called quasi-linear. If, $c_p = \text{const}$, $k = \text{const}$ the equation becomes

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \tilde{f}, \quad a^2 = \frac{k}{\rho c}, \quad \tilde{f} = \frac{\bar{f}}{\rho c} \quad (2)$$

here a^2 - temperature permeability coefficient.

Without separation from the generality one can consider $a=1$, then from (2) one obtains

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + f. \quad (3)$$

The first boundary issue is put as follows:

$\bar{D} = \{0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ we find the solution $u(x, t)$ of the following problem that is continuous in the field

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + f(x, t), \quad 0 < x < 1, 0 < t \leq T, \quad (4)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

$$u(0, t) = \mu_1(t), \quad u(1, t) = \mu_2(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T. \quad (6)$$

In this $u_0(x)$, $\mu_1(t)$, $\mu_2(t)$ - given functions. It is known that according to specific hypotheses about the smoothness of the exact solution, the solution to the (1)-(3) problem exists and is unique. The (1) - (3) problem solution satisfies the maximal principle and is continuously dependent on the initial and boundary conditions.

We solve this problem by the method of finite subtractions. For this to do this, step h with x on the variable, τ step by step t is a lattice in the following representation on a variable

$$\bar{\omega}_h = \{x_i = ih, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad hN = 1\},$$

$$\omega_\tau = \{t_j = j\tau, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, K, \quad K\tau = T\}.$$

(x_i, t_j) , $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$, $j = 0, 1, \dots, K$ points $\bar{\omega}_{h\tau} = \bar{\omega}_h \times \omega_\tau$ forms spatiotemporal web nodes (Figure 1). $I_0 = \{0 \leq x \leq 1, t = 0\}$, $I_1 = \{x = 0, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$, $I_2 = \{x = 1, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ lying in incisions (x_i, t_j) nodes $\bar{\omega}_{h\tau}$ the

boundary nodes of the lattice are called, while the remaining nodes are called internal nodes. In Figure 1, the marginal nodes are marked as crosses, and the inner nodes as circles.

Figure 1. $\overline{\omega}_{h\tau}$ spacetime web

A layer is said to be a set of all nodes of a $\overline{\omega}_{h\tau}$ lattice with the same coordinate in time. Thus the j -layer is said to be the following set of nodes

$$(x_0, t_j), (x_1, t_j), \dots, (x_N, t_j).$$

for a function $y(x, t)$ defined on a $\overline{\omega}_{h\tau}$ -net, we include the following designations

$$y_i^j = y(x_i, t_j), \quad y_{t,i}^j = \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau}, \quad y_{xx,i}^j = \frac{y_{i+1}^j - 2y_i^j + y_{i-1}^j}{\tau}. \quad (7)$$

Sometimes, to simplify writing, we drop the i and j indices and enter these designations $y_i = y_{t,i}^j, y_{xx} = y_{xx,i}^j$.

(1) the equation is described in Figure 2 for approximating the (x_i, t_j) point $(x_{i\pm 1}, t_j), (x_i, t_j), (x_i, t_{j+1})$ we enter a template consisting of four nodes. We replace the $\partial u / \partial t$ derivative at (x_i, t_j) with the $y_{t,i}^j$ subtraction relation, and the $\partial^2 u / \partial x^2$ derivative with the $y_{xx,i}^j$ second subtraction derivative. We replace the right side of the equation $f(x, t)$ with an approximate φ_i^j lattice function, as φ_i^j one can obtain one

$$\text{of the following expressions: } f(x_i, t_j), \frac{1}{h} \int_{x_{i-1/2}}^{x_{i+1/2}} f(x, t_j) dx, \frac{1}{h\tau} \int_{t_j}^{t_{j+1}} \int_{x_{i-1/2}}^{x_{i+1/2}} f(x, t) dx dt.$$

Figure 2. Subtraction scheme template for disclosure scheme

The result is the following subtraction equation

$$\frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{y_{i+1}^j - 2y_i^j + y_{i-1}^j}{\tau} + \varphi_i^j, \quad (8)$$

in this case, the subtraction equation approximates the given differential equation at (x_i, t_j) with the first order on τ and the second order on h . $\varphi_i^j - f(x_i, t_j)$ subtraction also has a smallness of the above order.

Subtraction scheme refers to a set of subtraction equations that approximate the basic differential equation at all internal nodes, and approximating – additive (initial and chegative) conditions at Boundary nodes.

References:

1. Alimardanovich N. T. et al. ODDIY ITERATSION USUL //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 160-168.
2. Alimardanovich N. T. et al. ZEYDEL USULI //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 169-176.
3. Alimardanovich N. T. et al. CHIZIQLI ALGEBRAIK TENGLAMALAR TIZIMINI ECHISH. ITERATSION USULLAR //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 153-159.
4. Alimardanovich N. T., Abduqodirovich N. N. PLASTINKA UCHUN IKKI O'LCHOVLI ISSIQLIK O'TKAZUVCHANLIK TENGLAMASINI SONLI YECHISH //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 15. – №. 3. – С. 141-143.
5. Alimardanovich N. T. CHIZIQSIZ TENGLAMALARNI TAQRIBIY YECHISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 323-327.
6. Kamolov, Dostonbek Rustam O'G'Li. "O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI." *Academic research in educational sciences* 3.NUU Conference 2 (2022): 348-352.
7. Хандамов И., Нуралиев Т. Teng qadamlar uchun nyutonning 1-interpolyatsion formulasi uchun algoritm va dasturiy ta'minot yaratish //Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 364-367.